

Strategy to Accelerate Bureaucratic Reform Towards a Golden Indonesia 2045

Radit Saputra ^{*1}, Irfandi Pratama ²

¹Department of Public Administration, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Muhammadiyah Mataram, Indonesia

²Department of Government Studies, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Sam Ratulangi, Indonesia

E-mail: raditsaputra@gmail.com

Abstract

strategy of accelerating bureaucratic reform as the main pillar in realizing the vision of a Golden Indonesia 2045. Adaptive, responsive, and technology-based bureaucratic reform is key to creating effective and globally competitive governance. The study uses a descriptive qualitative approach with secondary data sources from the relevant literature. The proposed strategy includes three levels of bureaucratic transformation: macro (institutional structure reform), meso (strengthening the governance architecture through SPBE), and micro (individual capacity development and ASN talent management). The implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) is considered an important instrument in supporting efficient and accountable public services. The case study of Polewali Mandar Regency shows good practices in the implementation of SPBE in the eastern region of Indonesia. In addition, ASN talent management is an important strategy in forming a professional and innovative bureaucracy. The results of the analysis confirm that structured and comprehensive bureaucratic reform is needed to achieve the national development goals as designed in the 2025–2029 RPJMN, towards an inclusive, sustainable, and progressive Indonesia.

Keywords: acceleration strategy, bureaucratic reform, Golden Indonesia 2045.

How to Cite: Saputra and Pratama. (2025). Strategy to Accelerate Bureaucratic Reform Towards a Golden Indonesia 2045

Copyright © 2025 by the Authors. Published by the GovPlan Indonesia Publisher. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the CC BY-SA Licence (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0>) .

Introduction

Indonesia is currently in an important phase in its development history (Kurniawan & Suswanta, 2022). Towards 100 years of Indonesia's independence, the government aspires to realize Indonesia as a sovereign, advanced, just and prosperous nation by 2045. This ideal is the forerunner of the Golden Indonesia 2045 vision. To achieve this, there are 4 (four) main pillars that need to be done, namely: (1) Human development and mastery of science and technology, (2) Sustainable economic development, (3) Equitable development, and (4) Strengthening national resilience and governance. The four pillars require quality and competent human resources (HR) in carrying them out, including the need for a better and progressive Indonesian government bureaucracy (Rudiyansah & Rezki, 2025).

An adaptive, *agile*, and *fluid* bureaucratic transformation is a non-negotiable necessity in the midst of such rapid global change, as well as increasing public expectations and demands for transparent, efficient, and high-quality public services (Simanjuntak et al., 2024). The bureaucracy can no longer rely on rigid and hierarchical conventional work patterns, but must be able to adapt to the dynamics of the times through a work system that is flexible, technology-based, and responsive to change (Yudhistira et al., 2024). The strategy of accelerating bureaucratic reform in this context does not only include administrative aspects, but also includes comprehensive improvements to government business processes, improving the quality of public services oriented towards public satisfaction, strengthening performance management based on output and outcomes, and implementing a transparent and integrated supervision and accountability system (Nanik, 2025).

The three main pillars that are important foundations in supporting this bureaucratic transformation are: first, strengthening the digital capabilities of civil servants as a response to the era of technological disruption and digital economy; second, the creation of an innovative and change-oriented organizational culture to encourage fast and appropriate decision-making; and third, increasing cross-sector collaboration with the private sector, civil society, and international institutions as a form of synergy in building an inclusive and globally competitive bureaucracy (Anwar et al., 2024). Thus, this strategy is expected to be able to accelerate the overall bureaucratic reform process as the main foundation to realize the big vision of a Golden Indonesia 2045. Through this research, it aims to identify strategic steps that need to be taken to accelerate Indonesia's economic development towards a developed country by 2045. By harnessing existing potential and overcoming various obstacles, Indonesia can realize its vision as an inclusive, sustainable, and prosperous developed country (Djajawinata et al., 2023).

This study also analyzes the Strategy for Accelerating Bureaucratic Reform Towards a Golden Indonesia 2045. has a very high urgency considering the challenges and opportunities faced by Indonesia in the coming decades (World Bank, 2022). One of the main reasons for its urgency is the need to understand and overcome the economic inequality that still occurs in various regions in Indonesia. This inequality not only impacts social inequality, but also hinders equitable and inclusive economic growth. Therefore, Indonesia needs strong, transparent, and accountable institutions (Sawitri & Mayulu, 2024). This study will examine how strategies for accelerating bureaucratic reform and improving public services can be optimized to support development goals. Identifying weaknesses and developing strategies to strengthen institutions will be key steps on the journey towards a Golden Indonesia 2045 (Harefa & Supriyadi, 2025). Overall, the urgency of this research

lies in the need to formulate policies based on comprehensive data and analysis. Thus, Indonesia can take appropriate and effective steps in achieving its vision as a developed country by 2045, which is not only highly competitive but also prosperous, inclusive, and sustainable (Widyastuti et al., 2024).

Research Methods

This study uses a descriptive qualitative analysis method with the aim of describing and analyzing in general the Strategy for Accelerating Bureaucratic Reform Towards a Golden Indonesia 2045 (Nawaludin, 2023). The type of data used in this study is secondary data sourced from relevant review literature. The secondary data sources include journals, books, related scientific articles that discuss related topics, The type of data used in this study is secondary data. This literature review serves to explore theories, concepts, and findings that already exist in previous research to deepen understanding of the topic being studied. The secondary data collected will be analyzed. For data analysis techniques, this study uses descriptive analysis. All data analysis results are presented in the form of descriptions that describe the main findings in a systematic and detailed manner. This description will help explain the phenomenon being studied, as well as provide a comprehensive overview of the Bureaucratic Reform Acceleration Strategy Towards a Golden Indonesia 2045 that is in accordance with existing data.

Results And Discussion

Three-Level Approach to Bureaucratic Reform in the Strategy of Accelerating Bureaucratic Reform Towards a Golden Indonesia 2045

To accelerate the achievement of Golden Indonesia 2045, the Indonesian government implements a bureaucratic reform strategy based on three levels of approach, namely the macro, meso, and micro levels. This approach is designed to build an adaptive, efficient, and real impact on society and national development. Each level has its own focus and role that synergistically supports each other. Therefore, the Ministry of PANRB develops a bureaucratic reform strategy through three levels, namely: Macro, Meso, and Micro.

Macro Level – Reform of National Institutional Structure

Through this level, bureaucratic reform is focused on designing a large design of state institutions that are adaptive, flexible, and dynamic as the main foundation for building a government that is able to respond to various challenges and changes that occur rapidly, both on a national and global scale. This reform at the macro level aims to create a cross-sectoral bureaucratic governance system that is comprehensively integrated between the central and regional governments, so as to create strong synergies in the implementation of public policies and national development. This approach is also designed to ensure that the bureaucracy has the ability to accommodate the changing direction and dynamics of development, such as digital economy transformation, climate change, and international geopolitical shifts that demand a rapid and coordinated response from all elements of the bureaucracy.

One concrete example of this macro-level reform strategy is the simplification of the organizational structure of government, which aims to eliminate overlapping authority and speed up the decision-making process. In addition, the coordination function between ministries/institutions is also strengthened, in order to create a more effective and efficient policy harmonization in the administration of government. On the other hand, optimizing the role of non-structural institutions is also an important focus, where these institutions are directed to contribute optimally through special functions that support the achievement of national development goals, without creating a fat and unproductive bureaucracy.

Reform of national institutional and bureaucratic structures can improve the effectiveness of public services, public trust, and governance. In addition, reforms can improve the national institutional structure Respect human rights, uphold the rule of law, Be accountable to their constituents

Meso Level – Adaptive Governance Architecture

This approach focuses on the development of governance systems and architectures that are flexible and responsive to the dynamics of change, both internal in the country such as bureaucratic efficiency demands, and external ones such as the development of digital technology and the need for service integration across sectors. This governance system is designed to be able to adapt to policy changes, social challenges, and the complexity of modern government administration. At the meso level, policy integration between sectors and strengthening bureaucratic digitalization are top priorities, because this is believed to speed up the coordination process, reduce bureaucratic silos, and increase the effectiveness of the implementation of government programs across agencies. One of the main instruments used to support this approach is the implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE), which aims to connect various public services and bureaucratic processes in one digital ecosystem that is efficient, integrated, easily accessible to the public, and able to encourage transparency and accountability in the administration of government (Handayani et al., 2025).

With bureaucratic reform, it is to realize good governance with high-integrity, productive, and excellent service apparatus in order to increase public trust, especially in responding to public demands for fast, transparent, and accountable services. This reform is also a strategic step in forming a professional work culture in government agencies, as well as a concrete effort to eliminate bureaucratic practices that are convoluted, inefficient, and less responsive to the needs of the community. Apparatus with high integrity is expected to be the main driving force in governance change, while the orientation to excellent service is a benchmark for the performance of the modern bureaucracy which will ultimately contribute greatly to increasing the legitimacy and public trust in the government as a whole.

Micro Level – Strengthening Organizational and Individual Capacity

At the micro level, reforms are directed at strengthening the internal capacity of the organization and the quality of individual bureaucrats (ASN), which are important elements in determining the effectiveness of the day-to-day administration of government. This strengthening covers various fundamental aspects, ranging from improving the quality of human

resources, structuring a more adaptive work system, to the application of technology to support performance efficiency. This approach includes competency development through continuous training that is adapted to the needs of the times, results-based performance management that can be objectively measured, the formation of a professional, disciplined, and public service-oriented work culture, and the digitalization of the ASN work system to encourage efficiency and transparency in the implementation of bureaucratic tasks. One of the important strategies put forward in this reform at the micro level is the implementation of national talent management, which is a system designed to ensure that civil servants are placed in positions that are in accordance with their best competencies, interests, and potentials, so that they are able to make maximum contributions according to their field of duty and contribute to creating a bureaucracy that is adaptive, innovative, and has a direct impact on society (Abadi & Dewi, 2024).

This three-level approach is a comprehensive effort that not only improves the bureaucratic structure institutionally and organizationally, but also substantially strengthens the governance processes and the quality of human resources of the state civil apparatus (ASN) which is the spearhead of public services. Structural improvements are directed at creating a leaner, efficient, and responsive organization, while strengthening processes is focused on simplifying workflows, increasing accountability, and integration across sectors through the use of digital technology. On the other hand, human resource development is carried out through improving competencies, forming an adaptive and innovative work culture, and implementing talent management nationally. With the strengthening at these three levels—namely the macro level (institutional structure), meso (systems and processes), and micro (individual capacity) the Indonesian bureaucracy is expected to be the main driving force in the success of the big agenda of Golden Indonesia 2045, which is to create a developed, highly competitive country, and be able to provide excellent and fair public services for all levels of society in facing increasingly complex global challenges.

SPBE Model as a Pillar of Public Service Modernization.

The Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) is a strategic approach in the modernization of public services, designed to transform traditional governance into a more integrated and information technology-based system as a whole. SPBE aims to build an integrative, dynamic, transparent, and innovative government, which is able to answer bureaucratic challenges in the digital era and meet public expectations for public services that are fast, accurate, and free from corrupt practices. In addition, SPBE is also aimed at improving the quality of public services that are integrated, efficient, responsive, and adaptive to various social, economic, and technological dynamics, through simplifying bureaucratic processes, eliminating duplication of services, and interoperability between government systems. The implementation of SPBE is an absolute prerequisite in realizing the vision of a Golden Indonesia 2045, because only with a modern, connected, and data-based government system, Indonesia can create a superior bureaucracy, be globally competitive, and be able to support the acceleration of national development in a sustainable manner.

Through the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) in the Strategy for Accelerating Bureaucratic Reform Towards a Golden Indonesia 2045, it is to create integrated, efficient, and responsive governance through the comprehensive use of digital technology. SPBE is designed to eliminate service fragmentation, simplify bureaucratic processes, and improve the quality and accessibility of public services.

Therefore, the Government of Indonesia has established several important regulations to support the implementation of SPBE, including:

1. Presidential Regulation No. 95 of 2018 concerning the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE), which is the main foundation in the digital transformation of government in Indonesia.
2. Presidential Regulation No. 132 of 2022 concerning the National SPBE Architecture, which regulates the basic framework for the integration of business processes, data and information, infrastructure, applications, and SPBE security to produce integrated government performance.
3. Presidential Regulation No. 82 of 2023 concerning the Acceleration of Digital Transformation and Integration of National Digital Services, which accelerates the integration of government digital services through the establishment of GovTech Indonesia (INA DIGITAL) as the operator of the government's digital service ecosystem.

The implementation of SPBE also supports four main elements in achieving long-term national development targets, especially in relation to "Golden Indonesia 2045", namely:

1. Equitable distribution of development through equal access to public services throughout the region.
2. Strong governance to support national stability.
3. Sustainable economic transformation through technology integration.
4. Digital literacy for the development of superior human resources.

With the existence of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE), it becomes a strategic pillar in bureaucratic reform, strengthening the digital foundation of government through the application of comprehensive and integrated information technology in all government agencies, as well as encouraging efficiency, effectiveness, transparency, and accountability in the implementation of public services. The crucial role of SPBE is not only limited to modernizing the administrative system, but also includes fundamental changes in the way bureaucracies work towards a collaborative and data-driven model of government. With the presence of SPBE, Indonesia's bureaucratic system is spurred to be more adaptive to the times and more responsive to the needs of an increasingly complex and dynamic society. Therefore, SPBE is a key element in accelerating institutional transformation towards

superior and competitive governance, as well as encouraging Indonesia consistently and directed in achieving the big vision of Golden Indonesia 2045, which is to become a sovereign, fair, and prosperous developed country in the midst of global competition.

This three-level approach is a comprehensive effort that not only improves the structure of the bureaucracy, but also strengthens its processes and human resources, through a series of integrated and sustainable strategies to create a bureaucracy that is adaptive, responsive, and able to face the challenges of the times. With the strengthening at these three levels—namely the macro, meso, and micro levels—the Indonesian bureaucracy is expected to be the main driving force in the success of the big agenda of Golden Indonesia 2045, by playing an active role in supporting economic growth, improving the quality of public services, and accelerating digital transformation and policy innovation that is oriented towards the interests of the people equally.

One of the steps to carry out digital transformation is to implement the eGovernment policy through the Presidential Instruction of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2003 concerning National Policies and Strategies for the Development of E-Government. The policy urges the central and regional governments to develop e-government in the implementation of public services.

For example, in eastern Indonesia, but nationally, the achievement of the SPBE index of local governments is still low, especially in the Eastern part of Indonesia. The data in diagram 1 below shows that the achievement of the 2022 SPBE index for Western Indonesia (average SPBE index: 2.45) has better achievements than Eastern Indonesia (average SPBE index: 1.96). This shows that the achievement of the SPBE index is still experiencing inequality between Eastern and Western Indonesia, mainly due to the digital divide (Sari & Winarno, 2012). The low SPBE index can have an impact on inaccurate data and information, budget waste, and low quality of public services (Altha, 2022).

Figure 1. Local Government SPBE Index in 2022
Source: Kemenpanrb (2025)

However, there are still local governments in the Eastern Indonesia region that are able to implement the SPBE policy properly and optimally. One of the local governments that is able to implement SPBE and develop optimally is Polewali Mandar Regency, West Sulawesi Province. Even though it is included in the Eastern Indonesia Region (Sulawesi, NTT, NTB,

Maluku, Papua), the Polewali Mandar Regency government has succeeded in realizing integrated services between regional apparatus optimally through the achievement of the SPBE index that it implements.

Figure 1. Trend of SPBE Acquisition Value in Polewali Mandar Regency
Source: (Ministry of Tourism, 2023)

In graph 2 above, there is a positive trend in the achievement of the Polewali Mandar Regency Government in implementing the SPBE policy. With this achievement, the Polewali Mandar Regency Government is the only region in Eastern Indonesia that has the title of "very good" and is included in the top 7 best nationally out of 483 provinces/regencies/cities that participated in the 2022 SPBE evaluation monitor. According to the Head of the Polewali Mandar Regency Diskominfo, the achievement of the Polewali Mandar Regency Government's SPBE index is driven by collaboration with stakeholders both from the policy formulation stage to implementation (Kominfo, 2023). Collaboration is indeed one of the strategies of the public sector in making a breakthrough or policy in various sectors, both the environment (Astuti et al. (2020; Torfing (2019), health (CrespoGonzalez et al. (2020), energy (Barsei & Sabtohadhi (2023); Naumann & Rudolph (2020), social and economic (Furqoni & Rosyadi (2019); Ji & Miao (2020), and digitalization (Febriyan et al. (2019); Lestari et al. (2021); Wilson & Mergel (2022)).

ASN Talent Management as an Acceleration Strategy

The development of ASN talent management is an important strategy in accelerating bureaucratic reform. These efforts include reducing dependence on external institutions in talent management, establishing internal units that handle talent management, and strengthening the meritocratic system to ensure professional and competent civil servants.

In addition, of course, bureaucratic reform is a crucial pillar in realizing the vision of a Golden Indonesia 2045. The main goal is to create a bureaucracy that is professional, has integrity, is high-performing, and is able to provide excellent public services. In this context, the Talent Management of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) plays a strategic role as the main accelerator.

There are some important ASN Talent Management in Accelerating Bureaucratic Reform at this time:

1. **Building Core Bureaucratic Capabilities:** The implementation of effective and comprehensively structured talent management will ensure that every government organization has a State Civil Apparatus (ASN) equipped with competencies, in-depth knowledge accumulation, and relevant and up-to-date technical and non-technical skills, so that they are able to carry out every mandated task and function efficiently, producing high-quality outputs, and have an effective positive impact on the achievement of organizational goals. This process fundamentally includes a series of strategic activities that include the early identification of potential talent, the provision of ongoing and personalized development programs, the placement of talented individuals in positions that best match their skill sets, and the implementation of a strong retention strategy to retain the best contributors to the organization.
2. **Encouraging Innovation and Adaptation:** State Civil Apparatus (ASN) who have superior talents and continue to develop their potential tend to show more creative characteristics in generating new ideas, more innovative in implementing solutions that have never existed before, and are more adaptive to various changes in the strategic environment, rapid technological developments, and the dynamics of increasingly complex and diverse public service demands in the context of the era of disruption. Characterized by rapid and unexpected changes, a bureaucracy that is systematically filled by individuals with qualified talents will have a much greater ability to proactively respond to various challenges that arise and produce innovative, effective, and efficient solutions to overcome the problems faced by society and the state.
3. **Improves Organizational Performance:** In general, individuals who have honed talents and are relevant to their field of work will show a higher level of performance compared to other colleagues. Therefore, by strategically placing these talented individuals in key positions that match their competencies and maximum potential, as well as continuously delivering development programs that are relevant to the needs of the organization and individuals, the overall performance of the organization will experience significant and continuous improvement, contributing to the achievement of the strategic objectives that have been set.
4. **Strengthening Leadership:** A well-designed and implemented talent management system not only focuses on the development of technical competencies, but also actively includes an early identification and structured development process for future leaders at various levels of the bureaucratic organization. The existence of strong, visionary, integrity, and inspiring leadership at all levels of the bureaucracy is a very important factor to effectively direct the course of the organization, motivate all team members, and implement the bureaucratic reform agenda consistently and continuously to achieve the goals that have been set.
5. **Creating a Positive Work Culture:** Government organizations that actively value contributions and systematically develop their potential talents are likely to form and maintain a more positive work culture, characterized by effective collaboration between team members, open and constructive communication, and a strong orientation to

- achieving superior performance. This positive work culture will in turn increase the internal motivation of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN) as well as increase their level of involvement in work and organization, which ultimately has a positive impact on productivity and service quality.
6. **Increasing Global Competitiveness:** In the context of increasingly fierce and dynamic global competition in various fields, including economy, technology, and innovation, the existence of an effective, efficient, responsive, and high-integrity bureaucracy is one of the essential competitive advantages for a country. The implementation of good talent management in the bureaucracy will significantly help create a State Civil Apparatus (ASN) that has global competence, international insight, is able to adapt to the best standards, and is ultimately able to compete effectively in the international arena, supporting a positive image and progress of the nation in the eyes of the world.

Therefore, ASN Talent Management is not just a trend, but an urgent need and a crucial strategy to accelerate Bureaucratic Reform towards a Golden Indonesia 2045. By identifying, developing, placing, and retaining talented civil servants, the Indonesian bureaucracy will become more professional, high-performing, innovative, and able to provide quality public services. Effective talent management implementation requires a strong commitment from all stakeholders, supported by clear policies, integrated systems, and ongoing evaluation. Thus, the potential of ASN can be optimized to realize the vision of a Golden Indonesia 2045. It is important to continue to monitor the development of ASN management policies and practices in Indonesia through official government sources and relevant publications to get the most accurate and up-to-date understanding.

RPJMN 2025–2029 as a Foundation for a Golden Indonesia 2045

The 2025–2029 National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN) was prepared as the initial foundation and concrete implementation of the first stage in the implementation of the 2025–2045 National Long-Term Development Plan (RPJPN), which is a long-term national development strategic document. This RPJMN is designed to map the direction of policies, priority programs, and national development goals in the first five years, in order to create synergy and consistency between medium-term planning and the nation's long-term goals. This document explicitly sets out the strategic steps that will be taken by the government in various development sectors as a concrete effort to realize the vision of the elected President of the Republic of Indonesia for the 2025–2029 period, namely "Together with Advanced Indonesia, Towards a Golden Indonesia 2045," which emphasizes inclusive economic growth, improving the quality of human resources, and effective and globally competitive governance.

To support the achievement of these priorities, the RPJMN 2025–2029 sets three main goals for national development:

- a) Reducing the poverty rate to 4.5–5 percent.
- b) Improving the quality of human resources, with the human capital index (IMM) targeted to reach 0.59.

- c) High and sustainable economic growth, with a target of reaching 8 percent by 2029.

Therefore, one of the flagship programs that is running at this time is the RPJMN in the year. 2025–2029 is a Free Nutritious Eating Program (MBG), which aims to build a healthy, intelligent, and productive Indonesian generation towards the upcoming Golden Indonesia 2045.

Conclusion

The strategy of accelerating bureaucratic reform is a fundamental step in preparing an adaptive, professional, and highly competitive Indonesian bureaucracy to welcome the Golden Indonesia 2045. Bureaucratic transformation is carried out through a three-level approach, namely Macro Level which emphasizes institutional structural reform to make the bureaucracy more efficient, responsive, and adaptive to global changes; The Meso Level which focuses on building digital-based and collaborative governance systems and architectures through SPBE; The Micro Level leads to strengthening the capacity of individuals and organizations through the development of ASN competencies and structured talent management. The implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) is one of the main pillars in supporting comprehensive bureaucratic reform, both in terms of public service efficiency, increasing transparency, and strengthening government accountability. Although there are challenges such as the digital divide between regions, as seen from the low SPBE index in the Eastern Indonesia region, there are still examples of good practices such as those carried out by Polewali Mandar Regency that have succeeded in implementing SPBE optimally. In addition, ASN talent management is an important strategy to ensure that the Indonesian bureaucracy is filled with quality, innovative, and service-oriented human resources. All of these strategies are in line with the policy direction in the 2025–2029 RPJMN, which is set as the initial stage of the implementation of the RPJPN towards a Golden Indonesia 2045, with a focus on inclusive economic growth, strengthening human resources, and globally competitive governance.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to express sincere gratitude to all parties who have contributed to the completion of this research. Special thanks are extended to the editorial team and reviewers of the journal for their valuable feedback and constructive suggestions that have significantly improved the quality of this article. The author also acknowledges the support from Universitas Muhammadiyah Mataram for providing the necessary facilities and academic guidance throughout the research process. Lastly, appreciation is given to colleagues and respondents who willingly participated and shared their insights during the data collection phase.

References

- Abadi, M., & Dewi, P. A. S. (2024). Situational Analysis of the Political and Economic Landscape in Indonesia towards 2045. *Annals Constantin Brancusi U. Targu Jiu, Letters & ...*

- https://heinonline.org/hol-cgi-bin/get_pdf.cgi?handle=hein.journals/ancnbt2024§ion=7
Anwar, D. S., Lestari, A., Atikasari, H., & ... (2024). ASN Cadre School: A Strategic Breakthrough for Preparing Future ASN Leaders with Integrity and Excellence Towards Indonesia Gold 2045. *Iapa Proceedings* <https://www.journal.iapa.or.id/proceedings/article/view/1211>
- Djajawinata, D. T., Permana, A., & Yudhistira, M. H. (2023). The Challenges of Infrastructure Development in Indonesia. In *Infrastructure for Inclusive* [eria.org. https://www.eria.org/uploads/08-PSN-Book-vol_1-ch_3.pdf](https://www.eria.org/uploads/08-PSN-Book-vol_1-ch_3.pdf)
- Handayani, I., Yosiana, C., & ... (2025). Reform of Environmental Approval Policy for Renewable Energy in Indonesia. In *Journal of* [journal.contrariusactus.com. https://journal.contrariusactus.com/index.php/JSDERI/article/view/101](https://journal.contrariusactus.com/index.php/JSDERI/article/view/101)
- Harefa, F., & Supriyadi, A. A. (2025). Leadership strategies for enhancing border security in Papua: A collaborative approach to surveillance and threat management. ... *Paradigm-Based Resilience Strategy*. <https://journal-iasssf.com/index.php/NAPBRES/article/view/1731>
- Kurniawan, C., & Suswanta, S. (2022). Implementation of Artificial Intelligence by the Government of West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) in Disaster Management. *International Conference on Public Organization (ICONPO 2021)*, 209(Iconpo 2021), 39–44.
- Nanik, F. R. (2025). Development and Threats of Artificial Intelligence in Industry and Workforce. In *European Journal of Social Sciences*. [iigdpublishers.com. https://iigdpublishers.com/storage/1IqpHMqn4z2t0kOG6MU1oQGnqksoU-metaRGV2ZWxvcG1lbnQgYW5kIFRocmVhdHMgODYtOTUucGRm-.pdf](https://iigdpublishers.com/storage/1IqpHMqn4z2t0kOG6MU1oQGnqksoU-metaRGV2ZWxvcG1lbnQgYW5kIFRocmVhdHMgODYtOTUucGRm-.pdf)
- Nawaludin, M. (2023). The Alignment Of The Planning And Budgeting Process For National Development Programs In Indonesia. In *Ritsumeikan Asia Pacific University*. [ritsumei.repo.nii.ac.jp. https://ritsumei.repo.nii.ac.jp/record/2000761/files/K118_sum.pdf](https://ritsumei.repo.nii.ac.jp/record/2000761/files/K118_sum.pdf)
- Rudiyansah, M., & Rezki, M. G. F. (2025). The Impact of Corruption on Economic Development and Community Welfare from Local And National Perspectives. *Abdurrauf Social Science*. <https://demo.nalanda.ac.id/journal.abdurraufinstitute.org/index.php/arsos/article/view/349>
- Sawitri, E., & Mayulu, H. (2024). Combatting stunting: The vital role of animal protein in early childhood nutrition. *Bioactive Compounds in Health and Disease-Online* <https://ffhdj.com/index.php/BioactiveCompounds/article/view/1419>
- Simanjuntak, R., Gusnar, I., Solihin, D., & ... (2024). Reactualization of National Resilience: A Historical and Conceptual Study. *Jurnal* <https://jurnal.lemhannas.go.id/index.php/jkl/article/view/558>

Widyastuti, T. V, Soponyono, E., Hamzani, A. I., Bawono, B. T., & ... (2024). The Impact of Food Law Policies on Local Community Empowerment in Indonesia's Sustainable Food Garden Program.

Indon. L. Rev. https://heinonline.org/hol-cgi-bin/get_pdf.cgi?handle=hein.journals/indolawrev14§ion=23

Yudhistira, M. H., Brodjonegoro, B. P. S., & ... (2024). Unlocking Urban Potential. *Bulletin of Indonesian* <https://doi.org/10.1080/00074918.2024.2389492>